

Towards effective protection of critical maritime infrastructures against low-cost threats

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Abstract—The protection of critical infrastructure is a growing concern. Maritime facilities are particularly vulnerable as they can be attacked not only from land, air or ships, but also from surface or underwater drones. This paper describes the architecture of a perimeter security system that can, in principle, detect, assess and track all types of these threats. As part of the architecture, time difference of arrival (TDoA) algorithms for localization and tracking are presented in this paper. It is shown experimentally that this technique is particularly suitable for the use of passive sensors. In the experiments, drones were successfully located in the air using passive-RF sensors. To cover underwater threats, it is proposed to complement this system with passive sonar. This type of sonar can probably even detect vehicles with low sound emissions based on changes in the ambient sound field. Some design considerations for such a sonar, its advantages and limitations are discussed.

This innovative methodology is versatile, and is suitable for a range of localization scenarios such as security, cyber radio-frequency (RF), and search-and-rescue (SAR) applications.

Index Terms—Maritime Critical Infrastructure Protection, localization, passive RF, Time-Difference-of-Arrival (TDoA), unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV), unmanned surface vehicle (USV), unmanned underwater vehicle (UUV), drone, sensors, sensing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent global events have prompted government and industry alike to rethink their approach to physical security. The threats we face are no longer large-scale military attacks from known adversaries outside our borders. Our fears today derive from the possibility that a small group of individuals, perhaps already within our borders, may have the ability to cause a large amount of damage. These attacks are likely to incur extremely high costs in terms of economic and environmental damage, gutted national morale, and loss of human life. Not only has the technology of the threat evolved, but recent events have redefined the very nature of the threat. No longer are the prime targets military in nature. Instead, public infrastructure and innocent civilians are facing attack.

Missiles, drones, surveillance tools and swarm attacks used to be confined to of the military realm. These threats could be countered with military solutions specifically set up to gain a crucial advantage in times of conflict. Money was not the prime concern. Today, workshop-made guided missiles, autonomous toys or do-it-yourself (DIY) drones, dinghies, and smartphones are only some of the potential outdoor threats facing every critical *maritime infrastructure*: ports, navy yards, ships at sea or off-shore installations. However, merchant

ships, container terminals, oil rigs and windfarms cannot all be protected with military-grade defenses and still be profitable.

Not only is the threat landscape developing: new detection technologies are entering the market as well. Above water, costly active systems such as radar are being replaced by passive RF-based localization and protection systems. These systems utilize effective low-cost sensors and vastly optimized algorithms, which make it possible to deploy these systems at an affordable price on every vessel and every fence line. Their functionality is on a par or exceeds the capabilities of optical or radar systems with vastly reduced uncertainty and analytic efforts and with greater resolution. While the solutions for the ground and airspace seem adequate, there is a gap with respect to underwater protection.

Some underwater studies have been published (e.g., [1]–[3]). Detecting potential submarine attackers requires specific approaches: microwave-based solutions do not work underwater and even advanced optical systems like LIDARs are limited to a range of a few meters. This makes underwater sound and sonar solutions the main tool in maritime surveillance. There are some key decisions to be made in the design of sonar systems: in order to achieve good angular resolution, the dimensions of the antennas must be large in relation to the wavelength. Since extended antenna systems are expensive, the use of short wavelengths seems attractive at first glance. However, sound waves of short wavelength are strongly attenuated and the range of operation is once again small. A detection algorithm has to consider other effects like multipath propagation due to reflections (for reference, see more details in [3]). Last but not least, there are various ubiquitous natural and artificial sound sources that create noise. Natural sound, for instance, emerges from surface waves and rainfall, and the artificial sources include ships and industrial operations.

To overcome these issues, this paper presents a cost-effective approach for airspace, terrestrial and underwater surveillance that implements the fusion of data from passive-RF and sonar sensors. By employing a Time-Difference-of-Arrival (TDoA) localization algorithm, the exact location of the target can be found. Their performance has been tested in the RF medium for airspace and terrestrial targets (e.g., [4], [5]), by and the smart use of antennas and beamforming (e.g., [6], [7]). To cope with the challenges of sonar, we harness the ambient noise as a sound source for a distributed system. Intruders modify the ambient sound field in different

Fig. 1: A typical TDoA scenario. Multiple receivers estimate the location of a target drone situated at $[x_t, y_t, z_t]$, where the i -th receiver is located at $[x_i, y_i, z_i]$.

ways: They add additional noise, generate extra reflections or shadow the ambient noise sources. The distributed network of small receivers is able to compare signals from different directions and find signatures that indicate critical situations. This approach endows underwater scenarios with the concepts and mathematics of passive detection and the algorithms used for airspace and perimeter monitoring.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the system model and the localization approach and Section III presents the design of an ambient noise sonar method. The description of the experimental results appears in IV. The conclusions are provided in Section V.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND LOCALIZATION APPROACH

This section provides an overview of the fundamentals of our scenario and the Time Difference of Arrival (TDoA) localization approach.

A. System Architecture

We start with a 3D scenario with M sensor receivers with known positions (see Fig. 1 for a visual representation):

$$\mathbf{p}_i \triangleq [x_i, y_i, z_i]^T, 1 \leq i \leq M. \quad (1)$$

Each receiver is equipped with a single antenna, and is connected to a central server for central processing. The working assumption is that the receivers are precisely synchronized.

The parameters of interest start with the coordinates of the drone target

$$\mathbf{p}_t \triangleq [x_t, y_t, z_t]^T. \quad (2)$$

The distance between the target and the i -th receiver sensor is denoted as r_i where the distances are expressed by the following equation:

$$r_i \triangleq \|\mathbf{p}_t - \mathbf{p}_i\| = \sqrt{(x_t - x_i)^2 + (y_t - y_i)^2 + (z_t - z_i)^2}. \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2: Sketch of the ambient noise imaging experiment in the San Diego Bay. The illustration is taken from [1].

where $\|\mathbf{x}\|$ is the norm of vector \mathbf{x} . The travel time of the signal (delay) from the target to the i -th receiver is:

$$\tau_i \triangleq \frac{r_i}{v} \quad (4)$$

where v is the respective wave speed. For RF, which is typically used in the air, v is given by the speed of light of roughly 299,792 kilometers per second. Underwater localization is typically based on acoustic signals, here v is given by the speed of sound of about 1500 meters per second. At the server, the signals received by the sensors are processed to compute the TDoA difference to derive the target location.

Given a dominant Line-of-Sight (LoS) component, the equation for the received signal at the i -th receiver is:

$$y_i(t) = A_i s(t - \tau_i - \tau_0) e^{j(\phi_i + t\Delta_i)} + w_i(t)$$

where $A_i = \sqrt{P} \cdot r_i^{-\alpha/2}$, and P is the target's transmitted power, $\alpha > 2$ is the path loss exponent, and $s(t)$ represents the symbol transmitted by the target at time t_0 (which is equivalent to the delay τ_0). The *phase shift* experienced by the traveling distance is expressed by $\phi_i = 2\pi f_c r_i / v$, and Δ_i indicates the *frequency offset* between the target and receiver i . The carrier frequency is f_c . It is assumed that the noise, $w_i(t)$, follows a Gaussian continuous process independent of time and independent of $s(t)$. Further, we denote Δ_{ij} as the *frequency offset* between receiver i and receiver j with respect to the target.

Each receiver receives a signal of duration $T_0 \gg \max_{i,j \in \{1,2,\dots,M\}} (|\tau_i - \tau_j|)$:

$$y_i(t), \quad 0 \leq t \leq T_0 \quad (5)$$

and sends the received signal to the server.

The TDoA system is based on the localization algorithm described in [4], which presented a novel approach to the

Fig. 3: Sketch of the proposed ambient noise sonar adapted from [1].

TDoA localization problem. For simplicity, in this paper we reduce the 3D localization to a 2D-dimensional optimization:

$$\hat{x}_t, \hat{y}_t \approx \underset{x, y, \{\Delta_i\} \in \mathbb{R}^{A_i, \phi_i}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \max \tilde{\Lambda} \quad (6)$$

where $\tilde{\Lambda}$ is a function of the received signals from all the receivers, and the optimization considers the frequency offset between the target and the i -th receiver, Δ_i , the effective signal power between the drone and the i -th receiver, A_i , and the phase shift between the drone and the i -th receiver, ϕ_i . More details can be found in [4].

III. DESIGN OF AN AMBIENT NOISE SONAR

Several studies have examined the feasibility of detecting objects under water by measuring the ambient noise. This work is motivated in part by an experiment conducted in the San Diego Bay in the 1990s [1]. For reference, we provide a brief description of the experiment and its outcomes, followed by an outline of how modern receiving and data processing techniques can improve this system to make general applications feasible.

The setup is illustrated in Fig. 2. The receiver consisted of a spherical dish with a diameter of 3m that projected the incoming sound onto an array of 130 hydrophones. The sound data were analyzed in 16 frequency bins from 8.5 to 75 kHz. In several trials various objects with an approximate size of 1m were placed at a distance of about 30m from the sensor. The system could indeed detect these objects, but better detection was achieved in the higher frequency bins between 57 and 75 kHz [2]. The authors indicated that the acoustic noise in these frequency bands was mainly generated by snapping shrimp inhabiting the rocks surrounding the test area. This biological source is generally not present in for instance the North Sea. Rather the sources of passive sonar operation in other area like European waters are the bubble oscillations caused by breaking waves, rainfall and shipping noise. These noise

Fig. 4: Each PR sensor was deployed on the coastline with a solar panel. We used two omni receive antennas (in white) at each PR to receive the IQ data, and two omni antennas (in black) for the cellular modem to communicate with the AWS-based server. Multiple PR sensors were deployed, as depicted in Fig. 5.

sources vary considerably in intensity and frequency range depending on the environmental conditions; see for instance [8]. Roughly speaking, however, the main usable frequency band for ambient noise sonar operation ranges from 500 Hz to 25 kHz. Scaling the receiving dish to this frequency band leads to impractical large dimensions. This also applies to beamforming antennas which must be large with respect to wavelength to achieve reasonable directional performance.

This limitation can be overcome by the modified concept depicted in Fig. 3. Here the receiver is replaced by a set of distributed hydrophones which are kept synchronized by wire or radio links. The TDoA algorithms described above are used to localize events. Unlike conventional imaging or beamforming techniques, the receiving system generally does not need to be large in relation to the wavelength. This makes an ambient noise sonar operating at low frequencies viable.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section presents the experimental results of latlon estimated coordinates by our TDoA localization system that was strategically placed along the coast. The experiment was conducted on a beach near the city of Netanya, Israel. The deployment of the passive-receiver (PR) sensors, as shown in Fig 5, was a square field measuring 1km \times 1km. The flight zone was on the left side (West) above the sea. The flight pattern that was recorded in one of the experiments. These data were considered the “ground truth”.

Fig. 5: Deployment of multiple PR sensors during the field test. The enclosed area measures approximately $1\text{km} \times 1\text{km}$. Image taken directly from the user interface of the R2’s command and control (C2). The flight zone was on the left side (West) above the sea. The flight pattern was recorded in one of the experiments. These data were considered the “ground truth”. The PR sensors were positioned at 99 (Northwest), 96 (Southwest), 112 (Southeast) and 104 (North-east).

For the active emitter target, we chose a DJI Mavic 3 classic. The drone was flown mainly and uniformly above the Mediterranean sea. We used 4 sensors to test the robustness of the algorithm in real-time.

To assess the efficiency of the TDoA system, a drone was flown within the designated experimental zone as the system pinpointed its position. The drones application supplied GPS location data at a rate of 10 locations per second, enabling the calculation of localization estimation errors. Note that because the systems estimated positions were compared to GPS locations, the error results inherently include GPS inaccuracies. In addition to GPS inaccuracies, error results from GPS locations also include challenges posed by GPS jamming and spoofing events that may have occurred during the trial period.

The drone operator was located next to PR 96. Throughout the experiments, the drone traversed the entire experimental area, encompassing regions where localization is generally less precise. The altitude of the drone ranged from 35 to 100 meters, and its velocity ranged from 0 to 18 meters per second (mps). The drone’s cumulative flight time lasted roughly 15 minutes, during which time the system generated 860 location estimates. Fig. 6 showcases the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the errors corresponding to these location estimations. The localization error was defined as the absolute distance between our estimation and the “ground truth” provided by the GPS records of the drone. Remarkably, the system demonstrated good performance even with the drone’s fluctuating velocity and altitude. As can be seen in Fig. 6, 90% of the localization estimations exhibited an error of less than 30 meters, with a median error of approximately 18 meters.

The drone was flown at varying altitudes over the sea throughout the testing period. The sensors successfully identified and geo-located the drone with a high degree of accuracy, thus demonstrating their potential for robust drone detection

Fig. 6: CDF of the localization error. The localization error is defined as the absolute distance between our estimation and the “ground truth” provided by the GPS records of the drone.

in coastal environments.

These range, accuracy and identification data are crucial to developing a comprehensive drone detection system for our shorelines, that will improve security and safety in these areas.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a novel approach to protecting critical infrastructure in the maritime environment. The presented system architecture for a comprehensive perimeter security system employs passive-RF and ambient noise sonar technology to detect and locate threats in the air, land and underwater. Passive-RF and underwater sonar systems operate with very different parameters in terms of wavelength, frequency and propagation speed. It is shown that TDoA algorithms are well suited for both cases. A resulting concept for an ambient noise sonar with a distributed number of sensors is outlined.

Experimental results prove the robustness of a TDoA-based localization system for real-time position estimation. In these experiments, a drone flying over coastal area and above the sea was tracked by passive-RF sensors placed in the beach area. The system demonstrated satisfactory performance in terms of localization accuracy and latency, with 90% of the localization estimations exhibiting an error of less than 30 meters, and a median error of approximately 18 meters.

The TDoA localization system described in this paper provides a reliable and efficient real-time position estimation of UAS, thus paving the way for further implementation in various scenarios.

Future work will involve conducting underwater experiments to localize objects beneath the water’s surface. This will enhance our understanding of underwater object localization techniques.

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